

Derivation of Shannon's Entropy for Constraints Sum over i $g(e_i)P(e_i)$ with Probability $P(e_i)$ Part 2

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In Part 1, we argued that if one has a conserved quantity $g(e_i)$, as given in a constraint Sum over i $g(e_i) P(e_i)$, then one may solve for the probability distribution $P(e_i) = P_1(g(e_i))$ by considering a subset of $P_1(g(e_i))$ s such that $g(e_i)+g(e_j) = E_1$. Within this subset, one has a uniform distribution for $P_1(g(e_i))P_1(g(e_j))=P_1(g(e_i)+g(e_j))$ with P_1 unnormalized and this leads directly to $P_1(g(e_i)) = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$, i.e. the Maxwell-Boltzmann form. A uniform distribution implies a minimal amount of bias in keeping with the conservation of $g(e_i)$ which is equivalent to the global constraint Sum over i $g(e_i) P(e_i)$. We then suggested that the subset-uniform distribution-conservation result of $C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ implies that $\ln(P_1(g(e_i))) = -g(e_i)/T$.

In Part 1, we argued that this allows one to create a math function $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ which when maximized subject to the constraint Sum over i $g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i))$ yields $C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$. The idea of maximizing is justified, we argue because one already deals with a minimal amount of bias in the subset-conservation approach and so this minimal bias must carry over to the full $P_1(g(e_i)) = P(e_i)$ set subject to the constraint Sum over i $g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i))$. This led to the derivation of Shannon's entropy (equivalent to F) in Part 1 as a math function. Physically, it is known that if one has $P(e_i)$ and N particles, then $N P(e_i) = n(e_i)$. As a result, one may physically permute the N particles creating $B = N! / \text{Product over } i \text{ } n(e_i)!$ distinct arrangements. Now, there may be various different $\{ n(e_i) \}$ sets which respect the constraint Sum over i $g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i)) = \text{number}$, but yields different values for B . One wishes to have the maximum value of B as this represents minimal bias. Thus, we suggest that Shannon's entropy should be linked with a physical scenario.

The $P(e_i) = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ solution is an approximate one as $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ may include $e_i+e_j > E$ total, as is well-known. Given the uniform distribution from the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach for which $p(e_i)p(e_j)=p(e_i+e_j)$ ((1)), this result yields values for $n(e_i)$, $n(e_j)$ and $n(e_i+e_j)$. Such a result may be compared with approximations of $\ln(n(e_i))!$ (as one knows that approximations are being used). One finds that the common Stirling approximation is implied by ((1)) so that the Shannon's entropy expression is equivalent to B in the Stirling approximation. Thus, Shannon's entropy is linked to a physical global feature and is not simply a mathematical expression.

Subset-Uniform Distribution- Conservation Approach

In Part 1, we argued that if one has a probability distribution $P(e_i)$ subject to a constraint: Sum over i $g(e_i)P(e_i)$, one may consider $g(e_i)$ to be a conserved quantity and solve the problem using the notion of a uniform distribution for

$P_1(g(e_i))P_1(g(e_j))= P_1(g(e_i)+g(e_j))$ ((2)) for P_1 unnormalized, with $P_1(g(e_i)) = P_1(e_i)$.

This leads to the solution $P(e_i) = P_1(g(e_i)) = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ ((3))

No notion of Shannon's entropy is needed. ((3)), however, required that one work within a subset of $P(e_i)$'s i.e. $g(e_i)+g(e_j) = E_1$ and one may rightly argue that there should exist an approach which applies globally, i.e. not within this subset or some other. This is why we introduced a global function $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ in Part 1 and showed that the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach allows one to explicitly find F such that the maximization of F with respect to $n.P_1$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i))$ yields the same solution as the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach. We show the details in the next section. This F is Shannon's entropy.

Now $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ is a math function and we ask: Is it linked in any way to a physical scenario? We note that the subset-uniform distribution-conservation is directly linked to physical elastic two body scattering and suggest that $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ should also have a physical interpretation which we consider in the next section. The catch is that the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach is an approximation (as we show in the next section) and so any physical interpretation of F must also be considered in terms of an approximation as well.

$P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ for P Unnormalized and Stirling's Approximation

$P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ ((4)) for $P(e_i)$ unnormalized is an approximation because it is possible for $e_i+e_j > E_{total}$ for N particles

Furthermore, given $P(e_i)$, multiplying by N , the number of particles, yields $NP(e_i) = n(e_i)$ ((5))

In Part 1, we created a math function $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ and maximized it subject to $P_1(g(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i))$. In order to find F , however, we used the subset-conservation approach which yields:

$\ln(P_1(g(e_i))) = -g(e_i)/T$ for P_1 unnormalized ((6))

This yields F as Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$. Physically, however, if one has $n(e_i)$ numbers then one may calculate the total number of distinct arrangements:

$N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$ ((7))

It is possible to have different $\{ n(e_i) \}$ sets satisfy: $\sum_i g(e_i) P(e_i) = \text{number where } n(e_i) = NP(e_i)$. One wishes to have the set which maximizes ((7)), in order to minimize bias.

The subset-conservation approach should not only yield a math expression for Shannon's entropy, as it did in Part 1, but should also provide some insight into $n(e_i)!$ $\ln((7))$ as an approximation, as $C_{exp}(-g(e_i)/T)$ is an approximation itself.

We try to find out what the subset-conservation approximate approach implies as an approximation for $n(e_i)!$.

One may compare the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach to a well-known approximation for factorials, namely Stirling's approximation to see if the two match or not. Stirling's approximation is:

$$\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) \quad ((8))$$

We showed in Part 1, that:

$$d F(P_1(g(e_i))) / dP_1 = -g(e_i)/T \text{ (for maximization)} = \ln(P_1(g(e_i))) + C \text{ from the subset approach} \quad ((9))$$

The subset-conservation approach is consistent with Stirling's approximation and maximization of ((7)) subject to the global constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) n(e_i) = \text{number}^2$ which maps to the global constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P(e_i) = \text{number}$, showing that one may maximize ((7)) with respect to the global constraint, but only under the Stirling approximation in order to have a result which is consistent with the approximation implied by the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach. As a result, Shannon's entropy is not simply a math function, but under the Stirling's approximation, which is consistent with the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approximation, it also represents the physical number of arrangements of N identical particles with $n(e_i)$ having e_i . Since one is only interested in e_i , one considers each particle within $n(e_i)$ as identical in terms of permutations, i.e. ((7)).

If one did not know Stirling's approximation, then one would find that the approximation consistent with the subset-uniform distribution-conservation approach was indeed the Stirling's approximation form.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we showed in Part 1, that given a constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P(e_i)$, one may consider a subset of all $P(e_i) = P_1(g(e_i))$'s such that $g(e_i) + g(e_j) = E_1$. Here $g(e_i)$ is considered to be a conserved quantity and one may consider physical 2-body elastic scattering. This leads to $P_1(g(e_i)) P_1(g(e_j)) = P_1(g(e_i) + g(e_j))$ or $P_1 = C \exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ as shown in Part 1. We then argued that if one does not wish to solve the problem in the subset space of $P_1(g(e_i))$ s, one should be able to solve it globally, i.e. involving all $P_1(g(e_i))$ s. This led to the creation of a function $F(P_1(g(e_i)))$ such that when maximized subject to the constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P_1(g(e_i))$ (where $P(e_i) = P_1(g(e_i))$), one obtains the subset-uniform distribution-conservation result. In other words, the subset approach fixes the form of F which turns out to be Shannon's entropy.

In this note, we argue that Shannon's entropy should be linked to some physical scenario. We note that the subset approach yields $P_1(g(e_i)) = P_1(e_i)$ and that $n(e_i) = N P(e_i)$, where N is the total number of particles. We also note that the subset -uniform distribution -conservation result $P_1(g(e_i)) P_1(g(e_j)) = P_1(g(e_i) + g(e_j))$ is an approximation because $g(e_i) + g(e_j)$ may be larger than a total value which holds for the N particles. The form $\exp(-g(e_i)/T)$ drops quickly and so these larger values may still be used in an approximation as is well known. Thus, any physical interpretation of F must be considered in light of approximations as well.

We point that there exists a physical situation linked with bias, namely the permutation of N particles with $n(e_i)$ being the number with e_i . Given that one is only interested in the value e_i , one has $B = N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$ as the number of distinct permutations. It is possible to have different sets of $n(e_i)$ satisfy the constraint, but yield different B values. One wants the largest B values to have the minimum bias. We show that the Stirling approximation, and maximization of B subject to the constraint $\sum_i g(e_i) P(e_i)$ is equivalent to the subset-uniform distribution -conservation approach. If one did not know Stirling's approximation, the subset -uniform distribution -conservation would have shown that $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ is the approximation consistent with F , i.e. Shannon's entropy found in Part 1 and the factorial expression, $N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$.